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RESIDENTIAL URBAN PATTERNS (DAMASCUS)

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Annotation: This article deals with the study of the change in the shape of buildings, their specifications and characteristics, and the building style that prevailed during the period of their construction.

Keywords: the history of Damascus, housing patterns, old Damascus, traditional housing, random housing

The introduction:

Damascus is the oldest capital in the world that has never been abandoned, and this city accompanied various civilizations and left a great and rich legacy in it so that no corner of its corners or one of its stones is devoid of the scent of this remnant history.

These civilizations have left a clear impact on the urban landscape in the city of Damascus, in addition to the changing and evolving need of people from time to time in order for the urban form to become suitable for human needs as this need is closely related to the change in the shape of the building and its construction method, and to clarify these changes, the article dealt with a study of several models of patterns. Residential construction dating back to different periods of time from the traditional to the contemporary and studying the change in the shape of buildings, their specifications, characteristics, and the style of construction that prevailed during the period of their construction.

Residential urban patterns in the city of Damascus:

Traditional Housing Pattern:

This pattern is found in the old city of Damascus inside the walls and some areas outside the wall as well. Traditional housing was designed and built by the residents according to their needs and social rules, using the materials available to them (stone – mud – milk – wood), and in these dwellings the owner enjoys full freedom. On his home and his environment, within an urban context characterized by the characteristics of the traditional city, as old Damascus contains relatively small residential areas that contain a homogeneous community whose members have religious relations and special social norms, in which the rich are bordered

with the poor and share the existing services, this pattern remained in the city of Damascus until a late period From Ottoman rule [1-4].

The traditional city of Damascus is characterized by a hierarchical hierarchy of spaces, where the transition takes place from public to private spaces within the residential area, that is, from the main public street to the secondary leading to the neighborhood, and from there to the alleys and the inner courtyard, in addition to the separation of trade functions from housing jobs, where the activities of trade diminish whenever We headed towards residential areas, residential areas characterized by an organic overlay and winding alleys, and these are the spatial features of Damascus as a traditional city.

In the old city of Damascus, the compact urban fabric was used, as it is an urban style in which the architectural blocks of buildings are juxtaposed, and it is characterized by the factor of flexibility and adaptation in its planning, and it is also distinguished by its high specificity and its distinctive identity.

Therefore, the traditional city is characterized by the progression in its urban fabric at all levels, such as the city and the heritage fabric, to the residential areas and at the residential unit level as well. This gradient reaches the interior of the inner courtyard of the house within the heritage fabric, where the spaces of the house are distributed around it and give a sense of the gradual order, and this is what provides a safety factor and a greater protection for the population from strangers [5-7].

Individual privacy is clearly shown through the design pattern of the residential unit, which is characterized by the following:

1. Directing the housing unit inward by opening it to the inner courtyard.
2. The closing of the housing unit from the outside, with less or no windows overlooking the alley or street, except for the mashrabiyas through which passers-by are seen without being exposed to them while the windows of the rooms are opened to the inner courtyard.
3. The entrance to the housing unit is shattered and slanted to ensure that the internal activities of the house are not exposed to the gaze of strangers outside.
4. The method of construction was local par excellence, according to local experiences, and the construction is carried out in accordance with the needs of the population and their social status, as well as local building materials that are distinguished by durability and permanence, such as stone [2-6].

Non-local Housing Pattern.

1. French Housing Pattern:

The dwellings placed within this classification represent the transitional phase from traditional architecture to contemporary architecture, as the dwellings were designed according to the style of the French cities prevailing in that period and belonging to the school of (the Bouzar) regular geometry.

The French took control of the city in 1924 AD, and this continued until 1946 AD, and the first organizational chart for the city of Damascus was drawn up by the French architect and planner Ecochar in 1936 AD, according to the rules that prevailed in French cities in the nineteenth century, while the second organizational chart It was put in place by Ecochar and D'Angé in 1960, in order to contain the great expansion of the city that took place in that period.

The concept of spacing of buildings from each other appeared, and the houses opened to the street that formed the structure of the modern city, and the buildings abandoned their side characteristics, as well as abandoned their low compact mass and replaced them with juxtaposed blocks of height, as the hierarchy of space was canceled, and the inhabitant became directly moving from the street level to the dwelling.

Most of the buildings were somewhat suitable for the prevailing climate that tends to heat and drought, which required an architectural method of adapting to its conditions, serving the human being, whether in the summer when the inhabitant needs to leak air currents, or in the winter season when the heat gain must be preserved [5-8].

Local building materials were used, such as stone, but with some differences in the construction method, such as the use of concrete for the roofs, and the ecosystem based on openness to the interior was abolished, as the emergence of modern transportation since the twentieth century was the most important factor in modifying the urban system of cities. It imposed a system of wide and straight streets, and then imposed an architectural system in harmony with the urban planning and new street shapes.

Architecture has become a product of new technologies, skills, and used materials, and it is subject to conditions and laws specific to the western style of building, but building materials and construction sentences are characterized by durability and permanence, and the style of construction has also differed, so we are in front of units with specific areas and without the concept of the courtyard as the human scale that allocates architecture to its inhabitants and not to the city, and solution The mathematical scale that seeks to achieve the harmony of the architectural blocks and their spaces with the system of intersecting streets, and the chess system that prevailed in classical times, in the Greek or Roman city, also appeared in the Baroque stone decorations that moved to it (ready-made), from Italy and Germany, to become A starting point for organizing modern cities.

2. The Global Trend Housing Pattern:

These houses were built after independence from the French occupation in 1942 by the state or by construction contractors, and if Damascus was liberated from the occupation, architecture has not been liberated, and it still follows the imported western pattern.

A major change has occurred in the housing pattern, due to the widespread introduction of reinforced concrete and the development of building codes or regulations that prevailed during this period, in addition to the social and economic developments of society. This style of housing is dominated by the housing of small families, where the children separated from the parents in the desire to live away from the patriarchal family that was prevalent in traditional architecture.

Therefore, the housing converged, and became small in size, following the system of apartments, whether high or connected separate buildings, and the orientation towards the outside became through the openings of the large external facades. It was used extensively by government agencies and construction contractors, after the colonial period that the Arab countries went through and is still used today, and its emergence coincided with the development of regulations, laws and legislation.

Due to the dependence of the dwellings of this style on abstraction and reductionism, this helped create environments whose function is to contain contemporary human activities, and to meet some needs, especially housing, regardless of whether this housing suffices the needs of families, and thus privacy problems have arisen and try to preserve it. Transfer and amend jobs in the housing in accordance with their needs, such as joining balconies and building annexes.

As for the construction method, it has changed, so we are in front of ready-made units with specific areas that do not take into account the real requirements of the family, and also do not achieve the conditions of sustainability and do not comply with the local climatic conditions, but the need for energy sources is higher to secure heating and cooling instead of adopting a local environmental building method that provides Energy and preserving it. There is no longer a clear use of local building materials, rather the use of concrete has spread as it has become the cheapest and most widespread material, and urban expansion has spread at the expense of green spaces with high density.

3. Squatter Settlement Pattern:

Squatter Settlement is areas whose housing was built without a permit and on lands owned by the state or owned by others, and these homes are often built outside the scope of government services and do not have adequate services and government facilities because the state does not recognize them, and the phenomenon of random housing is due to many reasons, including population growth, internal migration, and others.

During that period, migration from the countryside increased due to the weakness of the service structure and the desire for new job opportunities, and from here the problem began to escalate, and the population density in the city and its surroundings increased very quickly, contrary to what the city had planned for, and recorded the highest population census in its history within a short period of

time. It reached its climax at the end of the nineties of the last century, and due to the extremely high prices of regular housing, those expatriates found no escape except in relying on agricultural or protected lands to build housing that does not depend on the slightest technical or sanitary conditions.

The randomness of housing construction, and the ill-considered integration of the population, created a state of turmoil among the residents of those areas, resulting in various manifestations such as the spread of thefts and the emergence of fights continuously, but the difference in the entrance in each housing unit from the other and the presence of winding and narrow lanes may add a safety factor to the residents.

Large percentages of housing were constructed without proper construction camels, and with cheap building materials that are not durable, and are often built by their owners, and transportation and communication problems have arisen, so there are no paved asphalt roads except in a limited range, as well as drinking water, as residents of these neighborhoods are forced Indiscriminate purchase of drinking water, lack of modern electricity network and lighting; If any, it is done illegally.

The building materials used in the construction of slums are characterized by being light, not long-lived, quick to build, and their financial costs are low. They have lost the aesthetic element, although the mass overlay of the housing may give form cohesion, but it does not fulfill environmental or engineering requirements, but rather seeks to achieve the function only.

Conclusion:

We have also seen that the city of Damascus is passing through, like other Arab cities, in a state of turmoil at the urban level, due to external reasons resulting from an attempt to impose new urban patterns that do not respect the traditional local context as in the global housing pattern, and we cannot hide the internal reason that came as a result of the absence of curricula and solutions that seek to deal with these imposed patterns and develop them in line with the needs of the times.

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